

GERB-HR-ED01 rsut 1hrCM

**TOA outgoing shortwave radiation, monthly-mean diurnal cycle
resolving each day into 1-hour means**

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1. Intent of This Document and Point Of Contact

1a) This document is intended for users who wish to compare satellite derived observations with climate model output in the context of the CMIP/IPCC historical experiments. Users are not expected to be experts in satellite derived Earth system observational data. This document summarizes essential information needed for comparing this dataset to climate model output. References are provided at the end of this document to additional information.

This GERB dataset is provided as part of an activity to increase the usability of GERB satellite observational data for the modelling and model analysis communities. This is not currently a standard GERB satellite instrument product, but does represent an effort on behalf of the GERB project team to identify a product that is appropriate for routine model evaluation. The data may have been reprocessed, reformatted, or created solely for comparisons with climate model output.

Users of these data should ensure they reference Harries *et al.* (2005) in any presentations or publications.

Dataset File Name (as it appears on the ESGF):

rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_200701-200712.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_200801-200812.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_200901-200912.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_201001-201012.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_201101-201112.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-0_BE_gn_201201-201212.nc

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2. Data Field Description

CF variable name, CMIP short name, units:	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux, rsut, W m ⁻²
Spatial resolution:	1° × 1°
Temporal resolution and extent:	1hrCM (monthly-mean diurnal cycle resolving each day into 1-hour means), from 200705 to 201212
Coverage:	Area bound by 60°N/S by 60°E/W

3. Data Origin

The Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget (GERB, Harries *et al.* 2005), instruments operate on board the four Meteosat Second Generation (MSG, Schmetz *et al.* 2002) series of geostationary satellites. These satellites were subsequently renamed Meteosat-8 through to 11. The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers that make observations, approximately every 15 minutes, of the Earth's emitted longwave (~4.0 to 100 μm) radiation and reflected shortwave (~0.32 to 4 μm) radiation over

a geographical region roughly from 60°N to 60°S in latitude and 60°W to 60°E in longitude. Also onboard each of the Meteosat satellites is the Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) which provides observations of the reflected shortwave and emitted longwave radiances in narrow bands over the same nominal region but at a higher spatial resolution. Data from the SEVIRI instruments are used widely by the operational meteorological and research community and are employed in several steps in the GERB product processing.

The GERB reflected solar radiances are derived from the GERB observations (except for specific cases of filled data – described below) using information on the spectral properties of the scene, viewing geometry and solar illumination. Reflected shortwave radiation (RSW) fluxes are determined from these reflected solar radiances using empirically derived angular distribution models (ADMs). These ADMs have been built up from broadband observations obtained by the CERES instrument on the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) with some supplementation with models to fill in missing observational conditions (Loeb *et al.*, 2003). The appropriate ADM is chosen according to the underlying surface type (for GERB Edition 1 data this is a fixed surface type map), cloud cover, cloud optical depth and cloud phase which for GERB is retrieved from coincident SEVIRI shortwave channel radiances. Spatial information from the SEVIRI instrument is also used to correct for the spatial response of the GERB footprint.

It is important to note that there are two conditions under which the reflected shortwave fluxes are not derived from the observed GERB radiances: (1) clear ocean scenes within 15° of the glint angle and (2) twilight conditions defined as the solar zenith angle range 85° to 100°. In both these cases the radiance to flux conversion is not reliable and the fluxes are filled with a model compatible with the GERB data. In addition for solar zenith angles between 80° and 85° and over ocean when the glint angle is <25° the scene identification is interpolated from neighbouring times rather than contemporaneously inferred from SEVIRI. Users should note that data are not provided for the latitude bands from 55.5° to 59.5° N during November, December and January, and from 55.5° to 59.5° S during May, June and July each year owing to insufficient observational data.

For all of these conditions it is expected that the accuracy at the hourly timescale of the products will be lower. However, the bias will reduce when averaged over hours and should be negligible once averaged over the full diurnal cycle. Further details are provided in Russell, 2018.

The GERB Edition 1 level 2 standard data products released to the scientific community are determined from measurements obtained by the GERB instruments on Meteosat-8 and Meteosat-9. Comprehensive inter-calibration studies using coincident data from these two GERB instruments have been undertaken to ensure that the data from these two instruments are aligned to the same radiometric scale. A study performed by Parfitt *et al.* (2016), provided a correction to the GERB-1 products that must be applied to ensure these data are on the same radiometric scale as GERB-2, and also accounts for instrument aging effects. The resulting recommended “user” applied correction is detailed in Russell (2017) and has been applied to the Edition 1 GERB High-Resolution (HR) SW flux products used to generate the 1hrCM (monthly-mean diurnal cycle resolving each day into 1-hour means) *rsut* products described in this technical note. The GERB HR data products are specifically designed to enable the creation of spatial and temporal averages. They are resolution enhanced snapshots at the SEVIRI acquisition time, every 15 minutes, on a fixed equal viewing angle grid matched to 3 × 3 SEVIRI pixel grid-boxes.

At present, only data from the GERB instrument onboard Meteosat-9 (GERB-1) have been processed for submission to the obs4MIPs archive covering the period from May 2007 until December 2012. However, during this period, owing to operational constraints of the GERB instrument, data are only

available for six months of each year. These are the same for each year: January, May, June, July, November and December.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the processing chain employed to generate the 1hrCM *rsut* product. There are four main stages. The first is to take the Edition 1 GERB HR SW flux data with the user corrections applied and generate an albedo using knowledge of the incoming SW flux for each location and time. The albedo is then area weighted to create a 1° by 1° spatial resolution albedo for every 15 minute time interval. These data are then averaged over time to produce an hourly averaged albedo product for each day and converted back to TOA SW flux by multiplying the albedo by the incoming solar flux at the midpoint of the hour. Finally a monthly mean for each hourly time step is calculated. The number of data points (days per monthly hourly average) contributing to each monthly hourly mean are retained and are used to estimate the uncertainties associated with the product. This is discussed in more detail in section 4.

Important notes:

1. For an hourly average value to be produced for a 1° by 1° grid cell, at least one observation from the four observation times must exist for that grid cell.
2. Grid cells are considered to be in twilight when their central latitude and longitude have an associated solar zenith angle (SZA) for a 15 minute time in the range $100^\circ > \text{SZA} > 85^\circ$. Their flux is then set to that derived from a fixed twilight model (Kato and Loeb, 2003). Similarly, grid cells with $\text{SZA} > 100^\circ$ are considered night time points and their SW flux is set to 0.0 Wm^{-2} .

Figure 1: Summary of the processing steps employed to produce the GERB SW Flux obs4MIPs monthly hourly mean at 1° x 1°.

An example of the GERB monthly hourly mean reflected SW flux at the TOA (*rsut*) product for December 2012, plotted from 00:30 to 22:30 but only for two-hourly intervals, is shown in figure 2. There are many notable features including the contrast between the brighter desert surfaces (e.g. Sahara, Namib, and Kalahari), bright (reflective) clouds over tropical Africa and at the southernmost latitudes, and the darker clear-sky ocean surfaces.

Figure 2: Example GERB Edition 1 hourly monthly mean SW flux products (*rsut*) at 2-hourly intervals for December 2012.

4. Validation and Uncertainty Estimate

There are three main sources of error that have been considered which are the absolute accuracy of the GERB radiance measurement, the uncertainties in determining a flux from a radiance, and the impact of missing data on the average fluxes.

4.1 Absolute accuracy

Quoted bias errors for GERB reflected solar radiances are 2.25% for a typical full scale radiance ($240 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1}$). A detailed description of the absolute accuracy of the GERB reflected solar radiance measurements is discussed in Russell (2017) which considers the impact of uncertainties in the geolocation of the measured radiances, and provides cautions with respect to aerosols and thin cloud. Russell (2017) also provides details of the recommended user applied “SW combined correction” which accounts for the reduction in the GERB SW response due to instrument aging effects and unifies the records of the GERB instruments on Meteosat-8 and Meteosat-9. This user applied correction was applied to the GERB SW data used to generate the GERB *rsut* products in addition an adjustment to the GERB SW fluxes from the surface level to 20km level has been made to make them more compatible with model output (see Loeb *et al.* 2002)..

4.2 Radiance to flux uncertainties

GERB SW fluxes use the CERES TRMM ADMs for their radiance to flux conversion. Users are referred to the relevant CERES documentation and quality summaries for details concerning the accuracy of the ADMs themselves (see Loeb *et al.* 2003). GERB Edition 1 fluxes do not include an adjustment for the apparent aerosol optical depth and use interpolation of a monthly climatology to determine the wind speed for selection of the appropriate ocean ADM. Thus errors are expected to be larger in the presence of significant aerosol events. Comparison of co-angular fluxes between GERB and CERES indicates that differences in implementation including scene ID results in 1% elevation in SW fluxes due to the conversion as applied to the GERB products. The ADMs which are the basis of the radiance to flux conversions are statistical in nature and thus a random error will be associated with the instantaneous flux estimates: for the reflected shortwave the 1SD value of this error is 14 Wm^{-2} . Due to the fixed viewing geometry of the GERB instruments, for a given hour this error only reduces significantly in the monthly average if there is significant scene variability. For persistently clear scenes in particular it will likely remain of the order 10 Wm^{-2} in the monthly hourly average and present as a bias for that location and time. For regions where cloud conditions are variable, or for averages over different times of day the error is expected to reduce by the root of the number of different conditions and/or view geometry averaged.

4.3 Impact of missing data

Even for the months not affected by observing operational constraints, there are often days with missing hours. This occurs for a variety of reasons and tends to be relatively random with regards to timing. To assess the impact of such missing data on the quality of the monthly mean diurnal product, December 2012 data were used to investigate the effect on the *rsut* product of removing an increasing number of days before calculating the monthly hourly mean. Days removed were randomly selected, with 16 selection realizations used to assess the robustness of the results. The effects of removing blocks of successive days was also investigated for comparison.

Table 4.1 shows, for the December 2012 11:30UTC hourly average, the mean and standard deviation of the resulting error at the 1 degree scale due to one, two, three, four and five days of missing data. In all cases no significant overall bias is introduced, but the magnitude of the expected error at the 1 degree scale increases with the amount of missing data, as shown by the increase in standard deviation from just over 4 Wm^{-2} for one missing day to in excess of 9 Wm^{-2} for five missing days. The results in the table are determined over all the different realisations of the missing data but the pattern of missing days can contribute to the expected error. This can be seen in Figure 3 which shows the standard deviations for each individual realization as well as the impact of removing three consecutive days of data from the start, middle and end of the month. Overall the missing data studies indicate that, in general, the error in the monthly hourly mean *rsut* product at the one degree scale does not exceed the 10 Wm^{-2} 1 standard deviation error expected from the radiance to flux conversion as long there are no more than five days of missing data. To ensure that missing data does not become a dominant error term we therefore do not provide an *rsut* product for hours where there are more than five days of missing data in the month.

	SW flux uncertainty estimate (Wm^{-2})				
Number of missing days	1	2	3	4	5
Mean difference	-0.03	0.03	-0.03	-0.02	-0.01
Standard deviation	4.04	5.72	7.10	8.29	9.35

Table 4.1: Summary of the mean difference between no missing days and up to five randomly removed (missing) days in the hourly monthly mean centred at 1130 UTC. The standard deviation about the mean difference is also shown.

Figure 3: Impact on the standard deviation (σ) in the SW flux difference for an increasing number of missing days (N) within an hourly monthly mean (here shown for 1130 UTC for December 2012). Also shown is the impact on the standard deviation of removing three consecutive days at the beginning, middle and end of the month.

Figure 4 provides an overview of the availability of the monthly hourly mean flux products from 2007 to 2012. The figure highlights those recurring periods each year when data are not available owing to instrument operational constraints (areas in white), but also indicates those unplanned periods when numbers of missing data preclude the generation of the monthly average product (red). For those periods when monthly averages are generated, the figure shows the number of missing days for each month and hour; these are colour coded green for zero to three days and blue four or five missing days.

Figure 4: Summary of the periods when sufficient GERB-1 Edition 1 data are available to produce the *rsut* (and *rlut*) *1hrCM* products from 2007 to 2012. The *rsut* (and *rlut*) *1hrCM* products are only generated for those months and time slots highlighted in green (up to three missing days per hourly monthly mean) and blue (four or five missing days). Those periods in the record where the monthly products are not generated are shown in white and red. White indicates insufficient data owing to GERB instrument operational constraints, and red indicates an insufficient numbers of observations for other reasons.

Finally, as previously mentioned in section 3, there are insufficient observations (owing to the large SZA) in the latitude bands from 55.5 to 59.5° S during May, June and July, and from 55.5 to 59.5° N during November, December and January each year. Therefore, data for these locations and times are excluded from the data record provided.

5. Considerations for Model-Observation Comparisons

The GERB flux product are TOA fluxes referenced at the surface. Several issues should be borne in mind when comparing to shortwave fluxes under conditions of low sun (high solar zenith angles). For twilight conditions, defined as solar zenith angles between 85 and 100°, GERB SW fluxes are based on a fixed twilight model based on the CERES observationally derived twilight model (Kato and Loeb, 2003). This model is designed to avoid biases in global annual mean observations and is not expected to provide good local or time resolved accuracy. In addition, despite being based on observed radiances, the GERB SW fluxes for solar zenith angles between 75° and 85° are expected to be more uncertain due to the limitations of the radiance to flux conversion and difficulties in scene identification.

The GERB instrument is geostationary and has a fixed viewing geometry. This means that angle specific biases in the radiance to flux conversion can manifest and will be scene, location and solar zenith angle

dependent. In the shortwave the largest biases are seen over ocean when the glint angle is less than 20 degrees due to both the limitations in radiance to flux conversion and difficulties in reliable scene identification. The shortwave fluxes are also likely to have a larger error during significant aerosol events and over snow covered surfaces as the radiance to flux treatment is not optimized for these cases. Finally, as a fixed land surface model is used in the radiance to flux conversion, seasonal variations in anisotropy for regions with significant changes in vegetation such as a Sahel are not captured.

These products based on the GERB edition 1 dataset have a scene independent correction for instrument SW aging. This correction does not account for the different effect of aging on different scenes, overall it under-corrects the aging experienced for the bluest scenes such as clear ocean and over-corrects the aging effect for the least blue scenes such as desert. The residual errors are most apparent towards the end of the record (see Parfitt *et al.*, 2016).

6. Instrument Overview

The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers making measurements of the TOA outgoing radiation from the Earth over the wavelength range from 0.32 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$. The instruments are mounted on the MSG satellites which are spin-stabilised, and comprise of an optical and electronic unit. The optical unit contains the imaging optics and detector system, a despin mirror, quartz filter and two onboard calibration sources (visible and thermal). The electronics unit controls the optical unit and provides data handling. The detectors are arranged in a linear array of 256-pixels oriented north-south. The despin mirror is used to freeze the Earth view momentarily onto the detector array, adjusting the Earth's location by one pixel width for each rotation, enabling a full image to be built up over a period of approximately three minutes. The quartz filter is used to remove the infra-red component (4.0 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$) of the total incident radiation, thus providing a measure of only the shortwave (0.32 μm to 4.0 μm) component. The longwave component is derived by subtraction of the shortwave radiation component from the total radiation. The onboard calibration sources are used to monitor the performance and maintain knowledge of the instrument's calibration. A detailed description of the GERB instrument is provided in Harries *et al.* (2005).

7. References

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8. Dataset and Document Revision History

Rev 0 – 12 May 2020